

A Dual-Layer Gap Waveguide Antenna with Vertical Polarization for Full-Duplex Joint Communication and Sensing Systems

Reza Gheybi Zarnagh*, Abolfazl Haddadi†, Andrés Alayón Glazunov*‡

*Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands

† Gapwaves AB, Gothenburg, Sweden

‡ Department of Science and Technology, Linköping University, Norrköping Campus, Sweden

* r.gheybizarnagh@utwente.nl, † abolfazl.haddadi@gapwaves.com, ‡ andres.alayon.glazunov@liu.se

Abstract—A vertically polarized subarray antenna based on Gap Waveguide technology has been designed for Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) systems operating at the center frequency of 77 GHz. The proposed subarray consists of two radiating layers with an in-between cavity layer. The first layer is comprised of 3 up-pointing V-shaped slots with the inter-element spacing of λ and the second layer has 6 transverse-arranged slots that are employed to obtain vertical polarization. The $S_{11} < -10$ dB frequency bandwidth is from 75.7–78.3 GHz. The achieved peak Gain is 13.8 dBi at 77 GHz.

Index Terms—Joint Communications and Sensing, Gap Waveguide Technology, Isolation, Vertical Polarization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most research efforts on joint communication and sensing (JCAS) systems have been mainly based on single-beam transmitter and receiver antennas which may limit the sensing direction to the same as the communication direction. Recent studies have suggested using simultaneous distinguishable beams for communication and sensing separately [1]. A major problem that may arise in JCAS systems is the coupling of the transmit (TX) antenna and the receive (RX) antenna signal paths as well as the potential interference between radar and communication radiation patterns of the antennas [2]. Employing orthogonally polarized antennas is a well-known technique to increase the capacity and reliability of wireless systems. Benefits can be especially substantial for JCAS systems compared to single-polarized antennas [3], [4]. In [5], a shared aperture dual-polarized slotted waveguide antenna (SWA) is proposed to obtain a dual-polarized multi-beam antenna that can be realized for joint communication and sensing functionality. However, the limitation of the impedance bandwidth obtained with this structure impairs the benefit of the wide bandwidths provided at millimeter Waves (mmWaves). Gap waveguide antennas with the capability of guiding electromagnetic waves between pins without the need for electrical contact between the top and bottom plates provide low-loss transmission at mm-Waves and hence high gain antennas can be produced. For example, [6] presents a compact high gain horizontally polarized ridge gap waveguide slot array antenna for 77 GHz automotive radar applications.

However, when it comes to vertical polarization, there are some challenges with arranging slots in the radiating layer that may result in grating lobes. To overcome the problem of large grating lobes, one method is to apply metallic posts to locally alter the shape of the TE_{10} propagation mode supported by either ridge gap waveguides or ridge waveguides (see, e.g., [7]) which in turn degrades the impedance bandwidth of antennas.

In this paper, we have proposed a new method to produce vertical polarization with the ridge gap waveguide antenna. This enables the use of orthogonal polarizations for the communication and sensing parts of a JCAS system. The vertically polarized slot offers a complement to the horizontally polarized gap waveguide antennas mostly used in the literature. The following sections show the design process and optimized results for the proposed antenna.

II. DESIGN OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA

This section describes the design process of the vertically polarized subarray antenna. The proposed subarray antenna is simulated and optimized with the CST Microwave Studio simulation software. The antenna structure is a double radiating layer ridge gap waveguide illustrated in Fig. 1. As can be seen in Fig. 1, the first layer comprises three up-pointing V-shape slots and the length of each slot is about $\lambda_g/2$. The inter-element spacing is λ_g and slots are excited in phase. At the ends of slots, there is a cavity facilitating the rotation of electric fields. As can be seen from Fig. 2(a), which shows the electric field distribution in the V-shaped slot, the electric field arrows are perpendicular to the side walls of the slot. The superposition of the electric fields produces a total field in the longitudinal direction of the ridge which in turn produces vertical polarization. However, due to the λ_g spacing between the slots, grating lobes appear. In order to mitigate the problem with the high side lobe levels, the second layer is introduced, which consists of six transverse slots with an inter-element spacing of $\lambda_g/2$ as shown in Fig. 2(b). It can also be seen from the same figure that the electric field arrows are perpendicular to the large wall of slots and are tangent to the direction of the ridge. The second layer is directly excited through the cavity layer which has been optimized to ensure maximum matching

Fig. 1. Perspective view of the antenna.

Fig. 2. Field distribution of the slots (a) V-shaped slot and (b) transverse slot.

Fig. 3. Simulated Reflection Coefficient at 77 GHz.

between the two layers and connects the bottom radiating layer to the top layer.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the simulated results for the designed subarray are presented. Fig. 3 shows the return loss results for the antenna. The antenna operates in the 75.7 – 78.3 GHz frequency band and as shown a good impedance matching between the distribution layer and radiating layers has been achieved. The simulated E-plane ($\phi = 0^\circ$) and H-plane ($\phi = 90^\circ$) radiation patterns are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Co-polarized and X-polarized simulated patterns of the antenna at 77 GHz (a) E-plane and (b) H-plane.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a new method to design a vertically polarized subarray antenna based on the gap waveguide technology. The whole structure is comprised of multiple layers containing a distribution layer that guides the electromagnetic fields between the pins, a first radiating layer to configure the vertical polarization, a cavity layer to excite the second layer, and the top layer to compensate for the high side lobe levels. Given the presented simulation results, the proposed antenna is a good candidate for joint communication and sensing (JCAS) systems employing orthogonally polarized antennas to enhance isolation due to self-interference.

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